

Publish maps and models of species environmental niches and geographic distributions in Europe on OBIS

Deliverable 3.2

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The report represents the most up to date status of the information. Any potential upcoming information may be considered for incorporation in future deliverables to improve the scientific knowledge.

The MPA Europe project

MPA Europe is a project co-funded by the European Union (EU) that will map a network of locations representative of biodiversity in European seas (Atlantic Exclusive Economic Zones of the EU and its neighbours, and all the Mediterranean, Baltic, and Black seas) (Figure A).

Figure A. MPA Europe study area.

This network will indicate where to prioritise placement of Marine Protected Areas (MPA) for biodiversity protection and how Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) can maximise blue carbon benefits. By using a holistic set of biodiversity measures, from species to ecosystems (including habitats), and environmental data including carbon storage, water currents, and climate change velocity models, it will be possible to quantify and map both the present and future connectivity within the proposed MPA network. The multiple scenarios provided will support wider and improved MSP by policy makers, industry, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs). The major scientific areas of the project and its outcomes are summarized in the infographic presented in Figure B.

Figure B. MPA Europe project scientific areas

The inter-disciplinary approach of MPA Europe is supported by a diversity of partners. These include Nord University (Norway), the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO (Belgium), the Scottish Association for Marine Science (Scotland, UK), the Centre of Marine Sciences (Portugal), the Ocean University of China (China), Science Crunchers (Portugal), the University of the Ryukyus (Japan), Aarhus University (Denmark), and the Joint Nature Conservation Committee (England, UK). The partners include experts in marine biology, taxonomy, ecology, oceanography, biogeochemistry, and biogeography, MPA network design, benthic habitat mapping, carbon dynamics, species distribution, climate modelling, and MSP compose the MPA Europe team.

Deliverable 3.2 overview

This present document details the computational procedure, presents maps and the models for six hundred and six species chosen for testing the framework involved in Deliverable 3.2 of MPA Europe. It is expected that at least 15,000 species will be modelled until the end of the project. The information provided is crucial for policy-relevant research focusing on MPA designation, in particular, mapping biodiversity patterns, and will feed the main subsequent task of Prioritisation (WP5) of systematic conservation planning to design (prioritise locations for an) MPA networks.

Predicting the current and future distribution of European marine species

Abstract

Countries have committed to protect at least 30% of the world's land and sea areas by the year 2030 in a broader effort to address biodiversity loss. However, it is essential that the decision regarding the establishment of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) is informed by an understanding of how species are currently distributed and how it may be impacted by climate change. Here we developed a framework to provide European-wide distribution maps for more than 15,000 marine species. Species occurrences were sourced from two major biodiversity databases, the Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS) and the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF), by implementing pipelines that enable the integration of those two data sources. The framework includes automated steps for ensuring data quality and for running models under the Point Process Modelling approach, which is better suited for presence only models. We tested our pipeline with 606 species utilizing environmental data from the most recent version of the Bio-ORACLE database, with a fine resolution of approximately 5 km. Models were predicted for the current and future climate, considering five distinct Shared Socio-Economic Pathway scenarios (SSP1, SSP2, SSP3, SSP4 and SSP5) and two distinct periods (2050 and 2100). The resulting range maps were consistent with the occurrence data and generally demonstrated good predictive capacity (as indicated by the Continuous Boyce Index), though we anticipate potential areas for improvement. Distribution maps obtained with this framework can be used to derive the current and future state of biodiversity and guide future conservation planning.

Introduction

Species distribution modelling (SDM) has been extensively applied in deriving range maps for species on the recent years, including marine species (Boavida et al., 2016; Morato et al., 2020). Those models link the geographical information on the occurrence (and when available absence) of species to the available environment, establishing areas that present adequate conditions for the survival of the species (Elith & Leathwick, 2009; Pearson & Dawson, 2003; Peterson et al., 2011). Several algorithms exist for implementing SDM, with different complexity levels, and each modelling step should be carefully chosen to ensure reliable models.

Europe is presumably one of the best sampled regions in the world. Yet, a great part of its marine biodiversity may remain unknown (Appeltans et al., 2012). Some areas are better sampled than others (Hughes et al., 2021), a bias that can hinder our capacity of delineating correctly where protected areas should be established. Also, no consistent and harmonized map of biodiversity exists for the region. Here we provide a methodological framework to obtain European wide species distribution models for marine species. Using the methods proposed here we produced SDM for 606 species and predicted the potential distribution of species in five Shared Socio-Economic Pathways scenarios (SSP1, SSP2, SSP3, SSP4 and SSP5), for two future periods (2050 and 2100). Our findings indicate that this framework can be effectively applied to large geographic areas and with high number of species, yielding results of overall high quality.

Material and Methods

Study area

This study encompasses all areas within the Atlantic Exclusive Economic Zones of the European Union and its neighbours, as well as all the Mediterranean, Baltic, and Black seas Figure 1. This corresponds to an approximate area of 10.7 million km², of which approximately 10% are currently protected by Marine Protected Areas (MPAs). Since European seas represent one of the most extensively surveyed oceanic regions, it is possible to generate distribution models with greater confidence.

Figure 1. Area of study of the MPA Europe project. The dashed line depicts the expanded study area considered for model fitting.

When modelling species distribution, it is crucial for the study area to encompass a sufficient range of environmental conditions, enabling the models to distinguish between the conditions where the species thrive and those present across the geographical space. Consequently, an expanded area was considered for model fitting (ranging from 41°W to 47°E and from 20°N to 89°N). After model fitting and prediction, all maps were clipped to the study area.

Species occurrence data

Occurrence data were obtained from two global biodiversity databases: the Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS; <https://obis.org/>) and the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF; <https://www.gbif.org/>). OBIS boasts an extensive collection of over 115 million occurrence records and employs a rigorous quality control process, including taxonomic validation through World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS; <https://www.marinespecies.org/>). While GBIF covers a broader taxonomic range, encompassing both terrestrial and marine realms, it currently lacks the same level of quality control specifically tailored for marine species, as observed in OBIS. Therefore,

data selection procedures were implemented to ensure seamless integration of both data sources as explained in our previous report on Deliverable 3.1 (Principe et al. 2023).

A total of 30,007 marine species, found within the study area and with available occurrence records in at least one of the platforms, were included in the data cleaning process. This list excludes species from the Viruses, Protozoa, Fungi, Bacteria, and Archaea kingdoms, as the factors influencing their distribution may not be captured by the models implemented here. All species records from GBIF were cross-referenced with WoRMS to guarantee updated taxonomic assignment and alignment with OBIS data. Six hundred and six species were chosen for testing the framework and were modelled as part of this work. It is expected that at least 15,000 species will be modelled until the end of the project (see Appendix 1).

Data selection

Data selection is one of the primary steps in modelling species distribution and has a significant impact on model outcomes (Elith & Leathwick, 2009). Due to the large number of species, data cleaning procedures were carried out in an automated way. Initially, duplicated records were eliminated both between and within databases, utilizing a combination of the record's year and geohash (precision = 6). Additionally, records located on land were excluded. Lastly, for each individual dataset, only one record per cell was retained, maintaining the same resolution as the environmental layers (0.05 degree, approximately 5 km).

After completing this step, we conducted two outlier removal procedures for all records pertaining to each species, focusing on both geographical and environmental outliers (similarly to Vandepitte et al., 2015). Geographical outliers were assessed based on the average distance between the 15 closest records to each point. Our approach differs from previous analyses (which utilized distance to centroids, for instance; Vandepitte et al., 2015) in that it considers barriers (such as continents) when calculating distances, an important feature for marine species. For environmental outliers, we considered the mean bathymetry of records, retrieved using the “obistools” package (Provoost & Bosch, 2023). In both cases, a threshold of 6 times the Median Absolute Deviation ($6 \times \text{MAD}$) was applied for point removal (Leys et al., 2013; Vandepitte et al., 2015).

After those data cleaning steps were performed, we segregated the data for model fitting and evaluation whenever possible. To achieve this, for species with available data across multiple datasets, we computed, for each dataset, the count of available records (considering 1 per cell). For those datasets with a minimum of 10 records, we derived a metric quantifying the dispersion of points in the geographical space, known as *standard distance*. This step was taken to ensure that the evaluation dataset exhibited ample coverage and accurately represented the species' range. Subsequently, we excluded 50% of datasets with the lowest spread, and from the remaining set, one dataset was randomly selected for evaluation. The remaining data was aggregated to retain just one point per cell and was used for model fitting.

Spatial autocorrelation can potentially impact the specification of models (Dormann et al., 2007), leading to poor predictive and inferential power. Thus, before model fitting, we evaluated the spatial autocorrelation of the data using a straightforward yet effective method. Following Boavida et al. (2016), we generated a correlogram to assess the correlation between each predictor variable within various distance ranges. Then, for each distance class (applied in 5 km increments), a linear model was employed to test the correlation's impact on geographic distance. Following this procedure, the minimum non-significant autocorrelated distance was utilized to filter the occurrence records. Due to

the automated nature of this process, we set a maximum distance at which records could be removed to 50 km (approximately 10 times our resolution).

Environmental data

Biologically meaningful environmental variables were obtained from the project partner CCMAR who manages Bio-ORACLE v3, which provides harmonized marine layers with global coverage in a fine resolution of ~ 5 km (Assis et al. 2023). Ideally, layers should be selected based on the specific biology of each species. However, this approach becomes impractical when dealing with a large number of species. Thus, we divided species in four groups and chose variables that are deemed relevant for each one (Table 1). While at that moment only this set of variables were used, our framework includes the possibility of testing alternative hypothesis of predictor variables. In this sense, we plan to implement post-hoc tests to evaluate if the chosen variables are indeed the best to explain the group distribution. Because strong correlation between predictors can also have a negative influence in the models (Dormann et al., 2013), from a first list of variables we reduced it by removing variables with high Variance Inflation Factor (VIF), using a threshold of 5, assessed with the package “usdm” (Naimi et al. 2014). However, we have not automatically excluded all variables to achieve a certain level of VIF. Instead, we critically analysed the results to ensure that variables that we considered essential were included in the models.

We gathered information regarding the mode of life for each species by consulting the databases SeaLifeBase (<https://www.sealifebase.ca/>), FishBase (<https://www.fishbase.se/>) and WoRMS. All modes of life refer to the adult life stage. For pelagic species we used layers relative to the surface, while for pelagic species with notes associating it to the mesopelagic environment we used mean depth layers. For those benthic or demersal, the deepest (maximum) depth layers were used. If no information on the mode of life was found for the species, we further searched at higher taxonomic levels. If still no information was obtained, surface layers were considered for the species on model fitting.

Table 1. Environmental variables from Bio-ORACLE v3 (Assis et al. 2023) used for the environmental distribution modelling of marine European species. Variables were selected based in their biological importance for each group (in **bold**), which were defined according to higher taxonomic levels (indicated under parenthesis) following the classification available in the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS; <https://www.marinespecies.org/>). The depth used varied according to the mode of life of the species and to the availability of layers. Variables were calculated using the period of 2000 to 2010.

Variable name	Variant	Depth used
Fishes (Elasmobranchii and Teleostei)		
Sea surface temperature	mean, range	surface, mean, maximum
Salinity	mean	surface, mean, maximum
Sea ice cover	maximum	surface
Chlorophyll-a concentration	mean	surface, mean, maximum
Sea water speed	maximum	surface, mean, maximum
Bathymetry	mean	-
Photosynthesizers (Chromista and Plantae)		
Sea surface temperature	maximum	surface, mean, maximum
Salinity	mean	surface, mean, maximum
Sea ice cover	maximum	surface
Diffuse attenuation (KD490)*	mean	surface
Dissolved iron concentration	mean	surface, mean, maximum
Nitrate concentration	mean	surface, mean, maximum
Phosphate concentration	mean	surface, mean, maximum
Bathymetry	mean	-
Seabirds (Aves)		
Air temperature	mean	-
Sea ice cover	mean	surface
Phytoplankton (total)	mean	surface
Dissolved iron concentration	mean	surface, mean, maximum
Nitrate concentration	mean	surface, mean, maximum
Phosphate concentration	mean	surface, mean, maximum
Others		
Sea surface temperature	maximum	surface, mean, maximum
Salinity	mean	surface, mean, maximum
Sea ice cover	maximum	surface
pH	mean	surface, mean, maximum
Chlorophyll-a concentration	mean	surface, mean, maximum
Nitrate concentration	mean	surface, mean, maximum
Diffuse attenuation (KD490)	mean	Surface
Sea water speed	maximum	surface, mean, maximum
Bathymetry	mean	-

* Note: KD490 refers to the diffuse attenuation coefficient for downwelling irradiance at 490 nm

Environmental layers were obtained for three depths (surface, mean and maximum) for both the current period (2000-2010) and for two future periods (2050 and 2100) considering five distinct Shared Socio-Economic Pathways (SSPs) according to the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6; <https://wcrp-cmip.org/cmip-phase-6-cmip6/>): SSP126, SSP245, SSP370, SSP460 and SSP585. For model fitting, in instances where a layer indicating mean or maximum depth was unavailable, we substituted it with the surface layer. Additionally, if any layer was not accessible for

the future period, we retained the layer from the current period in the future predictions. Layers were downloaded using the “biooracler” package (Fernandez, 2023), which is a wrapper to the Environmental Research Division's Data Access Program (ERDDAP) infrastructure hosting the new version of Bio-ORACLE v3.

Testing with virtual species

To develop the framework and test the possible algorithms to be implemented, we created two virtual species (in which we have full control of the generative process; for more information on virtual species see Leroy et al. 2016 and Zurell et al. 2010). Because we know the true distribution of the virtual species, we can better explore the differences in performance of the distinct algorithms under distinct conditions (Meynard et al., 2019). We performed a set of testing considering the following scenarios:

- Two conditions of environmental data: all environmental variables known and one variable unknown (Gaussian noise)
- Two sampling conditions: with bias and without bias
- Two data availability conditions: low (30 points) and high (150 points)

This sums up to eight modelling settings. Because the sampling process of points is random, we generated 10 samples of presence points for each species (yielding a total of 80 models to be fitted). We also generated 10 samples (for each species) of presence-absence points to be used as independent evaluation datasets. Model fitting followed the same general methods of the framework (see next section), using environmental data from Bio-ORACLE v3, and tested the algorithms Generalized Linear Model (GLM), Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator (LASSO), Boosted Regression Tree (BRT), Maximum Entropy (Maxent) and Random Forest (RF), with different settings. More details about the testing with virtual species are available in the MPA Europe documentation: https://iobis.github.io/mpaeu_docs/methods-testing.html

SDM algorithm and model fitting

Species distributions were obtained considering a point process framework. Spatial Point Process Models (PPMs) are used to model events that arise as points in space (Renner et al. 2015). While these points are random in terms of their location and quantity, they are connected to an underlying process, which in our case, is associated to the suitability of habitat. Despite PPMs methods being widely used in spatial analysis (e.g., applications range from disease mapping to detection of landslides as in Lombardo et al., 2018), it was only recently that their application to SDMs gained momentum (Renner et al., 2015; Renner & Warton, 2013; Warton & Shepherd, 2010). These models are especially relevant for modelling presence-only data, where the sole available information pertains to the geographical locations where the species was observed (Fithian & Hastie, 2013).

While it is possible to adapt presence-absence methods for presence-only data, this involves the sampling of pseudo-absences (i.e., points that, in theory, should represent places where the species is absent). However, the number and placement of pseudo-absences can greatly influence models (Barbet-Massin et al., 2012). Differently, on a PPM framework, quadrature (or background) points are used as a statistical device to describe the available environmental space (Fithian & Hastie, 2013). Points are randomly sampled over the study area and the quantity of points can be determined based on the accuracy of the likelihood estimate (Renner et al., 2015).

PPMs are closely related to the widely used SDM software Maxent (Renner & Warton, 2013), which proved to produce accurate distribution maps. One important point to note is that *PPM predictions should not be interpreted as probability of occurrence, but rather as relative occurrence rates* (following Merow et al., 2013) as they measure the intensity of the occurrence of species (i.e., the records). Thus, all model predictions are expressed as a continuous value representing Relative Occurrence Rate (ROR). Provided that the occurrence points correctly reflect the underlying species occurrence (i.e., there are no significant biases), the ROR can be used as a proxy for environmental suitability.

Within this first application of the framework we selected two methods (LASSO and RF) which presented a good trade-off of accuracy and fitting/prediction time in a recent benchmark study (Valavi et al., 2022). We also based our choice in the results of the test with virtual species. In general, all algorithms tested performed well, except for Random Forest (without down-sampling), but the time for fitting and prediction varied significantly. Because we will run models for thousands of species, this is an important constraint that was considered in the subsequent steps.

LASSO is a regularized regression model (L1 regularization) that penalizes the coefficients, shrinking them toward zero (Friedman et al., 2010). Because LASSO can reduce the coefficients to exactly zero, it can remove variables and produce reduced models. LASSO is constantly applied to model species distribution (e.g. El-Gabbas & Dormann, 2018), and, in fact, is the underlying algorithm in the Maxent implementation in R (called “maxnet”; Phillips et al., 2017). RF is a machine learning algorithm that uses bagging to combine individual trees and minimize overfitting (Breiman, 2001; Valavi et al., 2021). Despite robust, RF models can suffer from class imbalance (i.e. number of points used in each category for the classification), a common problem when modelling species with presence-only methods. However, its application for PPM models proved possible through the use of down-sampling (Valavi et al., 2021).

Both models were fitted for all species with at least 30 records. The two algorithms used the same occurrence and quadrature points when fitting the distribution of species. The ideal number of quadrature points were obtained by fitting a Down-Weighted Poisson Regression with an increasing number of points and visually analysing when the maximum likelihood converged (Renner et al., 2015). Because running this analysis for each species would be unfeasible, we tested the ideal number of points with both virtual species and with a subset of 10 species. In all cases, there was little improvement in including more than 150,000 points, and we used this quantity for all species. Quadrature points were randomly selected from all valid areas within the environmental layers for each species. Before the sampling process, the study area was masked (on a per-species basis) to the maximum depth of occurrence for that species, with an added buffer of 300 m. This step was taken to guarantee that the model was not trained using environmental data from regions significantly beyond the species' suitability range (i.e., under the reachable areas; see Peterson et al., 2011).

All models were tuned to find the best combination of parameters using cross-validation (see next section). More specifically, for LASSO we chose the best lambda parameter and for RF the best number of trees. After the best parameters were found, the model was fit with the full data and then predicted for the current and future scenarios. Although thresholding SDMs should be avoided (Merow et al., 2013), for some applications (as ours) it is essential to have binary maps. Thus, we also generated binary predictions utilizing the P10 threshold. This threshold corresponds to the Relative Occurrence Rate (ROR) value that excluded the 10% of points with lowest ROR values. This thresholding approach offers the advantage of not being dependent on a specific evaluation metric, and therefore, it is not influenced by the characteristics of the quadrature sampling. For future predictions, the same thresholding value used for the current period was applied.

Cross validation and evaluation

Models were fine-tuned and assessed through cross-validation employing spatially segregated blocks. In this approach, the geographic space (i.e., the whole study area) is partitioned into several blocks with predefined dimensions, and all records within each of these blocks are assigned to specific subsets (folds) of blocks (in total, five folds). During each iteration, occurrence records and quadrature points from four of those folds are utilized to train the model, while one is reserved for evaluation (Roberts et al., 2017). Metrics are obtained for each run and then averaged across the blocks. Due to the omission of entire geographical areas in the training process, this approach is better suited for assessing the predictive capacity of models, particularly when the objective is to extrapolate to new time periods (Roberts et al., 2017). We used the function “cv_autocor” of the package “blockCV” to obtain the size of the block which better reflected the spatial autocorrelation of the environmental layers (Valavi et al., 2019). If the blocking procedure produced bins without any presence point, we attempted to adjust the block size by increasing or reducing it for a certain amount. Otherwise, if this procedure failed, random folds were used.

Evaluating presence-only models poses a non-trivial challenge. Here we applied two threshold independent metric (Area Under the Receiver Operator Curve – AUC, and Area Under the Precision Recall-Gain Curve - PRG) along with one presence-only metric (Continuous Boyce Index – CBI) to evaluate the models. True Skills Statistics (TSS), a threshold-dependent metric, was also calculated but was not considered in our model assessment. For TSS, we used the 10th percentile training present (P10) threshold. It is worth noting that there is criticism of using AUC to evaluate presence-only models, primarily because it treats background points as absences in its calculation (Jiménez & Soberón, 2020). However, in our case, AUC was used solely to compare the predictive performance of different configurations for each species, all subject to the same number of quadrature and presence points. As a general quality metric, we refer to the CBI.

All models were run in R version 4.3.1 (R Core Team). A list of the main packages employed in this work is available in Table 2. To ensure better reproducibility and to enable this same approach to be applied in other regions, the main framework for the development of the SDMs is available in an R package called “obissdm” (available at https://github.com/iobis/mpaeu_msdm). The code relative to the modelling of the European species is available at https://github.com/iobis/mpaeu_sdm. All decisions and procedures adopted to establish this framework are also documented on the MPA Europe documents, available at https://iobis.github.io/mpaeu_docs/.

Table 2. List of the main packages used in the species distribution modelling framework. Some packages are not available on Comprehensive R Archive Network (CRAN) and were downloaded from their GitHub repository. For a full list of all used packages, consult the GitHub repository https://github.com/iobis/mpaeu_sdm.

Package	Version	Citation	Availability
Occurrence data download			
rgbif	3.7.7	Chamberlain S, Barve V, Mcglinn D, Oldoni D, Desmet P, Geffert L, Ram K (2023). rgbif: Interface to the Global Biodiversity Information Facility API. R package	CRAN
robis	2.11.3	Provoost P, Bosch S (2022). robis: Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS) Client. R package	CRAN
Data processing and cleaning			
tidyverse (dplyr and tidyr)	2.0.0	Wickham H, Averick M, Bryan J, Chang W, McGowan LD, François R, Golemund G, Hayes A, Henry L, Hester J, Kuhn M, Pedersen TL, Miller E, Bache SM, Müller K, Ooms J, Robinson D, Seidel DP, Spinu V, Takahashi K, Vaughan D, Wilke C, Woo K, Yutani H (2019). “Welcome to the tidyverse.” <i>Journal of Open Source Software</i> , 4(43), 1686. doi:10.21105/joss.01686	CRAN
arrow	13.0.0	Richardson N, Cook I, Crane N, Dunnington D, François R, Keane J, Moldovan-Grünfeld D, Ooms J, Apache Arrow (2023). arrow: Integration to 'Apache' 'Arrow'. R package	CRAN
obistools	0.0.1	Provoost P, Bosch S (2023). “obistools: Tools for data enhancement and quality control.” <i>Ocean Biodiversity Information System. Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO</i> . R package	https://github.com/iobis/obistools
Spatial analysis			
terra	1.7-39	Hijmans R (2023). terra: Spatial Data Analysis.	CRAN
sf	1.0-14	Pebesma, E., 2018. Simple Features for R: Standardized Support for Spatial Vector Data. <i>The R Journal</i> 10 (1), 439-446, https://doi.org/10.32614/RJ-2018-009	CRAN
Model fitting			
glmnet	4.1-8	Friedman J, Tibshirani R, Hastie T (2010). “Regularization Paths for Generalized Linear Models via Coordinate Descent.” <i>Journal of Statistical Software</i> , 33(1), 1-22. doi:10.18637/jss.v033.i01	CRAN
randomForest	4.7-1.1	A. Liaw and M. Wiener (2002). Classification and Regression by randomForest. <i>R News</i> 2(3), 18--22.	CRAN

Package	Version	Citation	Availability
Plotting ggplot2	3.4.3	H. Wickham. ggplot2: Elegant Graphics for Data Analysis. Springer-Verlag New York, 2016.	CRAN
patchwork	1.1.3	Pedersen T (2023). patchwork: The Composer of Plots. R package version 1.1.3	CRAN
Others storr	1.2.5	FitzJohn R (2020). storr: Simple Key Value Stores. R package version 1.2.5	CRAN

Results & Discussion

Modelling the distribution of species can help overcome data limitations and produce accurate information on the current and future state of biodiversity. Aggregating SDM results can, for example, reveal stable areas that can be targeted for protection or areas that are prone to major changes and need to receive mitigation actions. Producing these range maps with a consistent coverage demands translating sparse data into models that correctly identify the relationship of species with its underlying environment, a task that involves several intertwined steps. The framework implemented here successfully fetched distribution models with high accuracy and relative fast implementation. At the same time, it points avenues for further improvement.

From the 606 modelled species, at least 410 had CBI values higher than 0.5 for RF and 352 for LASSO, an indication of the capacity of those models to correctly predict the occurrence of the species. Algorithms were able to converge in their results in both low and high number of occurrences (Figure 2). Models also showed similar responses in terms of future responses of species (see Figure 3 for an example).

*Figure 2. Species distribution predictions for three species with different number of records (A-C) according to two methods Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator (LASSO) and Random Forest (RF). Predictions are shown for the current period only. Relative Occurrence Rate (ROR) is the relative occurrence rate, with higher values indicating areas of higher suitability for the species. Species are (A) *Melanostomias tentaculatus* (36 records), (B) *Salpa maxima* (130 records) and (C) *Calonectris diomedea* (3,622 records).*

Figure 3. Species distribution predictions for the species *Raja brachyura* according to two methods Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator (LASSO) and Random Forest (RF). Predictions are shown for the current period (first column) and for three distinct SSP scenarios (SSP1, SSP2, and SSP5) for the year of 2100. Relative Occurrence Rate (ROR) is the relative occurrence rate, with higher values indicating areas of higher suitability for the species.

Both algorithms chosen for this first implementation of the framework shown similar results in terms of model quality (LASSO: $AUC = 0.86 \pm 0.09$, $CBI = 0.6 \pm 0.2$; RF: $AUC = 0.88 \pm 0.09$, $CBI = 0.5 \pm 0.2$) and time for fitting (LASSO: 4.4 ± 1.5 minutes; RF: 3.75 ± 1.8 minutes, Figure 4). The R package created to support this framework (“obissdm”; https://github.com/iobis/mpaeu_msdm) includes modules to fit four other algorithms (Maxent, Boosted Regression Trees, Generalized Linear Models and Generalized Additive Models), and we expect to include them on future modelling. Ensembling different models can also produce better predictions of distribution ranges (Hao et al., 2019; Valavi et al., 2022), and will be part of a next implementation of the framework.

Figure 4. Time for model fitting and prediction for species with different number of records using two distinct algorithms Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator (LASSO) and Random Forest (RF). Models were run in parallel, using seven cores.

Despite the positive results, there are some limitations that should be addressed in next versions of the framework. For example, our current approach limits the modelling to species with at least 30 valid (unique) records. However, modelling rare (or under-sampled) species is also important to accurately capture the state of biodiversity, and methods have been implemented recently to address this gap (Gaul et al., 2022; Mondanaro et al., 2023). One relevant point that still needs to be addressed is how to correct for sampling bias in the occurrence records, as this can lead to poor or wrong models (Baker et al., 2022). Even though Europe has a relatively good sampling coverage, certain regions may be disproportionately sampled for some species. This issue can become critical when there is a limited number of occurrence records available. Several methods were proposed to deal with sampling bias (e.g. Chauvier et al., 2021; El-Gabbas & Dormann, 2018; Nolan et al., 2022), but the large number of species and the automated nature of our framework imposes complications in its implementation. Therefore, further tests are needed before a definitive method can be applied.

It is also important to consider the limitations which are inherent to species distribution models. First, although we selected a set of variables which are linked with the species biology, other variables not accounted here may be equally important. Second, even if a strict quality control procedure is applied, species occurrence data may still present inaccuracies, which will affect the predictive capacity of the SDMs (Elith & Leathwick, 2009). Finally, other processes linked to the distribution of species (e.g. dispersion, competition) are not captured by SDMs (Peterson et al., 2011). However, when analysed critically those models can reveal spatial and temporal changes that

would otherwise be difficult to detect.

Countries are urged to meet their conservation targets in face of an accelerating impact of climate change on biodiversity (IPBES, 2019), a task that will demand high quality information on biodiversity. While model-derived distribution maps are not meant to substitute local scale data collection and monitoring, they are a valuable tool to overcome data and resources limitations (Elith & Leathwick, 2009). Our proposed framework adds to the effort of providing sound scientific knowledge to the marine spatial planning process by providing a robust platform to produce large-scale distribution models.

Data availability

The codes relative to the modelling of the European species are available at https://github.com/iobis/mpaeu_sdm.

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Appendix

Appendix 1. Maps of current period and future predictions of six hundred and six species chosen for testing the framework and modelled using the method of Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator (LASSO) and Random Forest (RF).

Important note: due to a problem reported in the platform (i.e. uploaded file is 5.9 GB but the maximum file size supported is 50MB), the additional information of the appendix should be requested directly to the PI of the MPA Europe project at Nord University
(<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10058739>)

